

Pneumocephalus: Rare Cause of Post-Operative Seizure

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ABSTRACT

Pneumocephalus is a rare complication associated with spinal surgeries and epidural anesthesia. A 60 year old female underwent total abdominal Hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy under general anesthesia with epidural analgesia. During immediate post-operative period, she complained of severe headache and had generalized tonic seizures followed by altered sensorium. Non-contrast CT head showed pneumocephalus. She was managed conservatively and did not have recurrence of seizure. This case report highlights the rare existence of pneumocephalus, 1-2% as per literature, and the same being a cause for seizure during post-operative period.

Keywords: Pneumocephalus; Epidural anesthesia; Seizure

INTRODUCTION

Common complications of lumbar epidural block include extended epidural blockade, unilateral analgesia, unplanned puncture of blood vessel or dura, post-puncture dural headache, subdural blockade, and placement of the catheter out of the epidural space, etc. ^[1]. Pneumocephalus (i.e. presence of air within the cranium) is a well described finding seen after head trauma or neurosurgical procedures but as a complication of lumbar epidural block, it has been rarely reported. It should be considered as a differential diagnosis while evaluating a patient with post-operative symptoms of headache, seizures,

focal neurological deficits. We describe an elderly lady who developed pneumocephalus following epidural analgesia and presented with severe headache and seizures.

CASE REPORT

A 60 year old lady underwent total abdominal hysterectomy and bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy under general anesthesia with lumbar epidural analgesia. During recovery from anesthesia, she complained of severe holocranial headache followed by generalized seizures and altered sensorium. She was afebrile, vital signs were stable, and had no focal neurological deficits. Computed tomographic scan of head showed pneumocephalus (Figure 1a & 1b). Other causes of peri-operative seizures namely sepsis, fever, drug reactions and electrolyte disturbances etc. were ruled out through appropriate tests. She was managed with intravenous midazolam followed by levetiracetam with termination of seizure activity. There was no other active management given for pneumocephalus. Imaging done after 2 weeks showed disappearance of pneumocephalus.

Figure 1: Contrast computed tomography of head [1(a)] and bone window [1(b)] showing pneumocephalus (arrow)

DISCUSSION

Pneumocephalus is a rare complication after epidural procedures described only in case reports^[2,3,4]. It occurs due to accidental dural puncture. Even 2 to 4 ml of air can cause symptomatic pneumocephalus^[5]. Signs and symptoms include headache, nausea, dizziness, altered sensorium and meningismus with

headache being the most common presentation. It can mimic Post Dural Puncture Headache or neuroinfection and needs to be ruled out.

The management of pneumocephalus varies. Untreated, the air usually disappears in 3–5 days due to reabsorption^[6]. In severe cases, administration of 40–100% oxygen has been suggested to hasten reabsorption^[6].

CONCLUSION

Pneumocephalus should be considered as a differential diagnosis in post operative headache and seizure, especially when epidural anesthesia is involved. This would ameliorate the tendency for extensive workup and consultation that would lead to exhaustion of precious emergency resources.

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